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Polytomous Item Sets in CAT:

Termination Criteria for Online Calibration

Zhuoran Wang
William Muntean
Joe Betts

Apr. 26, 2025

Background

--Polytomous item Set

- When multiple items utilize the same stimulus or a sequence of stimuli, these items form an item set.

Item	D_1	D_2	D_3
1	-2.27	0.17	2.3
2	1.73	2.35	2.64
3	-2.73	-0.55	0.31

Background

--Online calibration

- In CAT, OP items are assigned to candidates adaptively, so candidates' ability can be most accurately estimated.
- Online calibration is usually applied within a CAT.
- Online calibration assigns EXP items to candidates adaptively, so EXP item parameters can be most accurately calibrated.

Background

--Item set online calibration

- The goal of item set online calibration is to **estimate all item thresholds** in polytomous item sets **equally accurately**, while the **entire item set is assigned to a candidate at once**.

Research Design

Termination Criteria

- **Sample size:** An item/set was masked if it had been administered 250 times, representing the mean sample size for EXP items.
- **SEM:** An item/set was masked when all threshold SEMs were smaller than a defined value.
- **Step:** An item/set was masked when changes in all thresholds were less than a defined value.
- **No:** The baseline condition.

Results—Maximum RMSE

Results—Standard Deviation RMSE

Summary

- In item set online calibration, all thresholds ought to be estimated equally well.
- Four termination criteria were compared:
 - Sample size
 - SEM
 - Step size
 - No
- When using random EXP item assignment, SEM termination criterion works well. However, when using E-opt to assign EXP items, no termination criterion is needed.

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Credit: da-kuk

Questions?